

Solvent Extraction of Rhodium(III) with Benzil- α -Monoxime. Direct Photometric Determination in the Organic Phase

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A method is proposed for the extraction and simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III) with benzil- α -monoxime. In hot condition, rhodium gives a yellow chelate at pH 1-6 with the reagent, which is extractable into chloroform and the absorbance measured at 400 nm. Quantitative extraction occurs at pH 4-5. Beer's law is valid for 1-12 μ g Rh per ml. Optimum conditions for extraction, effect of pH, reagent concentration etc. have been discussed. Rhodium has been determined in presence of a number of cations and anions.

LITERATURE shows only a limited number of methods for the extraction of rhodium(III)¹⁻³, the metal ion being generally complexed with a suitable reagent in warming condition and the resulting chelate extracted with an organic solvent followed by spectrophotometric estimation.

In the present communication, the authors propose a method for the extraction and simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of rhodium(III) with benzil- α -monoxime. Previous use of the reagent was reported by Paria⁴ and Ueda⁵ to extract platinum and cobalt. Here the method is based on the fact that at pH 4, rhodium(III) forms a yellow complex with the reagent on warming. The chelate can be extracted into chloroform and measured photometrically at 400 nm. The optimum conditions for extraction, effect of pH, reagent concentration, diverse ions etc. have been studied.

Materials and Methods

Separating funnels were used for the extraction purpose. Absorbance measurements were carried out with the help of a Beckman DU2 Model Spectrophotometer with optically matched 1 cm quartz cells.

Chloroform was distilled before use. Benzil- α -monoxime was prepared in the laboratory⁶. All other chemicals used were either chemically pure or reagent grade materials unless otherwise mentioned.

A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving 0.2505 gm RhCl₃·3H₂O (Standard sample, Johnson & Matthey) in 50 ml distilled water. A test solution was prepared by suitably diluting a portion of this stock solution so as to contain 78.2 μ g Rh per ml and was used throughout the work. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared by standard procedures⁷.

Recommended procedure for the determination of rhodium(III):

An aliquot (2 ml) of rhodium(III) test solution containing 156.4 μ g Rh was placed in a beaker and

10 ml of buffer solution of desired pH was added. 2 ml of 1% benzil- α -monoxime in acetone was added and the solution was heated on a water bath for about 80 min to ensure complete complexation. When the colour was developed, the whole of the solution was transferred to a separating funnel with care. The solution was cooled and shaken for 5 min with 10 ml of chloroform. The beaker was washed with a further few ml of chloroform to avoid loss. After occasional shaking the layers were allowed to settle and the organic phase was transferred to a flask and diluted exactly to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the chloroform extract was measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank, prepared under identical conditions. Rhodium extracted was determined from a previously prepared calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The absorbance spectrum of Rh(III)-benzil- α -monoxime complex in chloroform, extracted as above, was taken against a reagent blank. The chelate shows strong absorbance below 350 nm and it decreases exponentially with increase in wave length and becomes insignificant beyond 460 nm. The reagent itself shows practically no absorbance from 380 nm onwards. All the absorbance measurements were performed at 400 nm because of moderate absorbance by the chelate.

The extraction behaviour of Rh was studied over the pH range 1-8. Quantitative extraction occurs at pH 4-5. Above or below this pH range, the extraction is found to be incomplete. Above pH 6.0 an emulsification at the junction of the two layers hinders the procedure. Attempts to minimise the emulsification were carried out by using some other organic solvents, but no better results were obtained.

The absorbances of the chloroform extracts, containing different amounts of rhodium extracted at pH 4, were measured against a reagent blank. In each case the aqueous phase after extraction was

free from metal ion. The results prove that the system obeys Beer's law closely at 400 nm over a concentration range of 1–12 μg of Rh per ml of the solution.

Measurement of the absorbance of the chloroform extract containing Rh(III)-oximate at different intervals of time shows that the colour system is stable at least for 12 hr.

Variation of the concentration and amount of the acetonetic solution of the reagent shows that 2ml of the reagent solution (1%) is suitable for the operation; lower concentration makes the process time consuming. Higher concentration was avoided because of reagent economy.

The molar absorptivity of the complex was calculated and found to be 6.9×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 400 nm (on the basis of rhodium content) and sensitivity of the colour reaction according to Sandell's definition was 0.015 μg Rh/cm².

The optimum period of extraction is 5 min within which period rhodium is completely extracted in a single operation.

Diverse ions :

Interferences due to a number of foreign ions have been tested during the extraction procedure at pH 4. It has been found that to determine 156.4 μg Rh the following ions may be tolerated when present in amounts (μg) shown in parenthesis : Magnesium(II) (4500); barium(II) (5000); strontium(II) (5000); manganese(II) (2000); lead(II) (4500); palladium(II) (4000); uranium(VI) (5000); arsenic(III) (4000); mercury(II) (5000); cadmium(II) (3500).

Palladium(II) (4000) was pre-extracted at the room temperature in order to avoid its interference. Beryllium(II) (3000), vanadium(V) (2000), chromium(II) (3000), cobalt(II) (1500), nickel(II) (2000), copper(II) (2000) show mild interferences. In presence of platinum(IV) (500) high result is obtained. It is obvious as Pt forms a coloured chelate in the same

condition and co-extracted. Ruthenium(III) and osmium(VIII) form an intense colour and black precipitate respectively when present. All attempts to mask these metal ions with different masking agents failed. Lanthanum(III), molybdenum(VI), tungsten(VI) and iron(III) prohibit complete colour development even in presence of weak masking agents. Among the anions tested, bromide(5000), sulfate(8000), nitrate(8000), phthalate(8000), phosphate(8000), acetate(8000), citrate(8000), arsenite(8000) do not interfere. The anions showing strong interferences are, EDTA, fluoride, iodide, thiocyanate and thiosulfate.

Reproducibility : Different amounts of rhodium were taken and determined by the recommended procedure. The results are accurate to within $\pm 2.1\%$.

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